
INDIAN CINEMA'S REFLECTIONS ON SOCIETY'S VIRTUES AND FLAWS: AN EXPLORATION

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.7757315

Abstract:

The recent years have seen a significant transformation in cinema. Its efforts to exhibit socially conscious and responsible films have broadened its role beyond that of merely providing moving pictures and have had a significant impact on millions of people. The movie business is gradually turning its attention to social concerns and hopes that the trial will increase public awareness of them. However, many image creators continue to employ the same picture-making method, which may negatively impact viewers. The purpose of the study is to examine the significant influence that Indian films have on audiences. In order to achieve this, it will discuss and examine both virtues and flaws. The purpose of this paper is to highlight the social objective of the movies, which sheds light on the evolution of the entertainment business. This study demonstrates that moviegoers enjoy these films, and it inspires upcoming directors and the media to consider social issues by including real-world events into their works.

Keyword: Social, Culture, Cinema, Reel, Real, Virtues, Vices, Influence.

Introduction:

One of the most effective and influential screenplay mediums for addressing many social issues is Indian cinema. Since their inception in 1913, movies have served as an essential medium for disseminating social thoughts and circumstances. It can be quite interesting to understand whether movies are influencing society or the other way around. Indian film has been experimenting with a variety of genres to

develop a winning formula that appeals to people and succeeds at the box office, from mythology to love to comedy to thriller and horror.

The most crucial tool for getting different social themes over to spectators has been the idea of parallel cinema, a very strong and beneficial departure from mainstream cinema. Through this alternative type of film, themes including sexism, female feticide, the caste system, dowries, AIDS awareness, and the stigma

associated with mental illness have been effectively brought to the fore. Since there may be a discrepancy between audience expectations and the actual goal of the art movie, the success of these films and, consequently, the conveyance of the social message, have not always been ensured.

Objectives:

The following primary objectives will be the focus of this paper:

1. To recognize the efforts made by filmmakers to creatively spread awareness of social concerns among the public using the most powerful type of media — cinema
2. To draw attention to the rising popularity among moviegoers in such films, giving young filmmakers the confidence to convey various social issues on the big screen by incorporating real life elements into the film.

Literature Review:

Researcher have studied related themes, papers, etc. the Media culture's products give us the tools with which to create our identities, sense of self, ethnicity, race, and nationalism, sexuality, and concepts of "us" and "them." Indian commercial cinema is the most effective communication tool in Indian society. The most popular mass media for interacting

with the public is film and cinema. Film assumes a foundational dimension as a humanistic discourse with the ability to change the cultural and material fabric of our daily lives because it serves as a mediator of social realities and personal hopes, of group problems and individual goals.

Discussion:

With an average of 800 to 1000 films produced each year; Indian cinema is the largest creator of feature films in the world, more than doubling the output of Hollywood. The Hindi-language film business in India is dominated by "Bollywood," which has its headquarters in Bombay, now Mumbai. Additionally, films are made in several regional tongues, like as Bengali, Tamil, Bhojpuri, to name a few. Although these films are successful domestically, the language barrier prevents audiences from travelling beyond state lines. Films are the most efficient medium for understanding and expressing to audiences social norms, attitudes, cultural nuances, and behaviors, especially in light of variety and audience reach. In addition to reflecting the society they are intended for, films also play a significant influence in influencing and forming that society. Since the beginning of the Indian film industry, the film community has experimented with a variety of genres in

an effort to convey societal concerns. Some of these efforts were a failure, while others were so well received by the general public that they broke box office records. This paper tries to look at a few films that became box office successes while also leaving a lasting impression on viewers or at the very least inspiring them to consider changing the world.

Limitations of These Studies:

It might be necessary to discuss at least one film each problem because the parallel cinema is dispersed throughout a wide range of societal issues at different levels of the Indian diaspora. The research in this paper may not cover all social issues, including those involving illiteracy, gender bias, and the right to equality, the Indian political system, same-gender relationships, and crime against women, female infanticide, and stigma surrounding mental health and awareness, environmental safety, and many others.

The box office may not accurately reflect audience perceptions that can be measured. According to history, failed movies often end up becoming cult favorites'. Therefore, qualitative reviews would provide a better understanding of the commercial success of films, particularly those from concurrent cinema.

Conclusion and Future Study:

The study successfully illustrates how realistic film influences, shapes, and moulds societal conventions and society while concurrently taking input from the same audience. Method acting has a significant, if not only, influence on how people's perceptions and opinions of the social issues that affect our society are formed. Some films, like "Rang De Basanti," succeeded in rousing the public and increasing awareness of the injustice in the real-life murder case of supermodel Jessica Lal.

Future research on this topic might cover a larger range of social topics and validate the changing preferences of modern audiences who want to see such serious issues addressed in a more objective and fair manner. This public support would motivate the mushrooming film industry to produce magic on screen beyond typecasts and educate moviegoers on more serious issues that need to be dealt with compassion and a feeling of urgency if society is to progress for the better.

References:

1. Anand, B.K. (2018). Looking at Student-Teacher Bonding through the Lens of Attachment Theories: A Study of Movies Black and TaareZameen Par. Literary Voice

- A Peer Reviewed Journal of English Studies. 1(9). 48-55
2. Atwal J., (2018). Embodiment of Untouchability: Cinematic Representations of the “Low” Caste Women in India. *Open Cultural Studies*, 2, 735-745
 3. Bhugra, D. (2006). *Mad Tales from Bollywood*. 18
 4. Butalia, U. (1984). Women in Indian Cinema. *Feminist Review*, (17), 108-110.
 5. Chakravarty, S. (1993) *National Identity in Indian popular cinema, 1947-1987*, University of Texas
 6. Dasgupta, R.K. (2012). Digital media and the Internet for HIV prevention, capacity building and advocacy among gay, other men who have sex with men (MSM), and transgender (TG): Perspectives from Kolkata, India. *Digital Culture and Education*, (4) Special Issue: The HIVe.
 7. Dastidar, S. G. and Elliott, C. (2019). The Indian film industry in a changing international market. *Journal of Cultural Economics*.
 8. Deakin, N. and Bhugra, D. (2012). Families in Bollywood cinema: Changes and context. *International Review of Psychiatry*, 24(2), 166-172